

Polarographic Studies on Influence of Concentration and Nature of different supporting Electrolytes on the Kinetics of Irreversible Electrode Reactions of DDD and BHC

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Polarographic behaviour of DDD and BHC in aqueous solutions containing 4% dimethylformamide (DMF) and 50% ethanol has been studied at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in Britton-Robinson (BR) buffer of pH 7.0 in presence of varying concentrations (0.05–0.50 M) of different supporting electrolytes, viz. tetrabutylammonium bromide (TMAB), KCl, KBr, KCNS, KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , and NH_4NO_3 . Each depolariser is reduced in two steps which are diffusion-controlled and irreversible. The kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{t,h}^0$) of the electrode reactions have been calculated by Koutecky's method. A decrease in the values of kinetic parameters shows that the irreversible electrode reactions of DDD and BHC tend to become increasingly more irreversible with the increasing concentration of different supporting electrolytes. The results have been explained in terms of double layer structure.

YAMAMOTO¹ reported the half-wave potentials of some insecticides, viz., DDD, BHC, rotenone and pyrethrin in dioxane using gelatin as maxima suppressor and Me_4NBr as supporting electrolyte at a constant pH. Heyndrickx and Maes² reported $E_{1/2}$ values of dieldrin, lindane, methoxychlor, thiodan and aldrin in 0.1 M LiCl and 0.01 M Me_4NBr . A survey of literature reveals that polarographic studies on the influence of the concentration and nature of different supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of DDD and BHC have not been reported so far. Hence the title study has been undertaken.

Experimental

Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethane (DDD) and benzene hexachloride (BHC) (Hindustan Insecticides Ltd.) were recrystallised from acetone before use. The other chemicals were of analytical reagent grade. Stock solutions of the depolarisers were prepared in dimethylformamide (DMF). The concentration of DDD and BHC (in aqueous 4% DMF and 50% ethanol) was maintained at 1.0×10^{-3} and 5.0×10^{-4} M, respectively. Desired concentrations of various constituents of BR buffer of pH 7.0 were added to the solution to be polarographed. As no maxima were encountered in the present study, the addition of suppressor was avoided. A Toshniwal CL 02 manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL 50 polyflex galvanometer was used. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.). The number of electrons (n) involved

in the reduction of DDD and BHC was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon³. This gave the value of n equal to 2 for each step of DDD, while n equal to 2 for the first step and 4 for the second step for BHC. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of the diffusion coefficient (D) of DDD and BHC at various concentrations of supporting electrolytes. The potential-dependent rate constant $k_{t,h}$ was calculated by Koutecky's method^{4,5}. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{t,h}^0$ were calculated⁶ from the plots of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. Throughout the measurements the current at the end of the drop (i.e. maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites⁷. The d.m.e. had the following capillary characteristics (in 0.1 M TMAB, open-circuit): for DDD, $m = 2.18 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 3.2 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.04 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$, $h_{\text{corr}} = 43.4 \text{ cm}$; for BHC, $m = 2.8 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 3.0 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.38 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/6}$, $h_{\text{corr}} = 46.5 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

At pH 7.0 of BR buffer with increasing concentrations (0.05–0.50 M) of TMAB, KCl, KBr, KNO_3 , KCNS, NaNO_3 and NH_4NO_3 , DDD and BHC yield two well defined reduction waves. The reduction of each depolariser is diffusion-controlled as evidenced by the fact that the plots of i_d vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ are linear and pass through the origin. Millicoulometric studies reveal that each step of DDD corresponds to a 2-electron reduction process, while in the case of BHC the first step corresponds to a 2-electron reduction process while the second one to a 4-electron process. Thus, the overall reduction processes of DDD and BHC involve 4 and 6

electrons, respectively. Various criteria of ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of DDD and BHC in presence of increasing concentrations of different supporting electrolytes were applied. The slope values of log plots in respect of each reduction step are much larger than the theoretical value expected for a 2- or 4-electron reversible reduction process. From this it follows that the polarographic reduction of DDD and BHC is irreversible⁷. Further, the theory of irreversible waves^{8,9} predicts that the current is independent of the pressure head of mercury at the foot of the wave and it becomes diffusion-controlled at the top, varying linearly with $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$. This dependence of the current on h_{corr} at different stages of each reduction wave of DDD and BHC was also studied and it was found that the current was independent of h_{corr} at the foot of the wave whereas it was proportional to $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ at the plateau of the wave. This study clearly shows that the polarographic reduction of DDD and BHC is totally irreversible.

The polarographic characteristics, viz. i_d , $E_{1/2}$ and D of each depolariser were determined in the presence of increasing concentrations of different supporting electrolytes, and the typical values in respect of TMAB are presented in Table 1. It is seen that a decrease in i_d of each depolariser occurs as the concentration of the supporting electrolytes is gradually increased. This may be attributed to the increase in ionic strength of the medium¹⁰. Further, in the case of DDD with increasing concentrations of TMAB, KCNS, KNO_3 and NaNO_3 , the $E_{1/2}$ values of both the steps shift to more positive potentials, while a negative shift occurs in the presence of increasing concentrations of KC, KBr

and NH_4NO_3 . On the other hand in the case of BHC while a positive shift occurs with increasing concentrations of TMAB, KCl and KBr, a negative shift is observed with KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , KCNS and NH_4NO_3 . In each case the plots of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ in the presence of different supporting electrolytes are linear (Fig. 1) thereby showing that there is only one rate-determining step^{11,12} involved in the electroreductions of DDD and BHC. From these plots the values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{t,h}^0$) have been obtained at different concentrations of supporting electrolytes and the typical values in respect of one supporting electrolyte (TMAB) are listed in Table 1. The values of potential-dependent rate constant, $k_{t,h}$ at a potential, which lies between the potentials corresponding to the foot and the plateau of the polarographic wave, have also been obtained, and the typical values in respect of TMAB are presented in this Table 1. Recently, Singh and coworkers¹³⁻¹⁶ have pointed out the inherent limitations of $k_{t,h}^0$ in the interpretation of the results regarding the effect of various experimental conditions on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode processes, and have put forward that this aspect can be studied in terms of the value of $k_{t,h}$ at a potential which lies between the foot and the plateau of the wave. Therefore, on the basis of the values of αn_a and $k_{t,h}$ (at a selected potential) the following results have been obtained concerning the influence of concentration and nature of different supporting electrolytes on the kinetics of the irreversible electrode reactions of DDD and BHC.

Electrode reaction of DDD: It is found that with the increasing concentrations of KCl, KBr and NH_4NO_3 , the value of $k_{t,h}$ decreases while it

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF DDD AND BHC IN PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF TMAB

pH=7, Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°

[Supporting electrolyte] M	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	αn_a	$k_{t,h}^0 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$	$k_{t,h} \times 10^4 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ (at selected potential, V) (S.C.E.)	
Electrode reaction of DDD								
0.05	I	4.60	0.49	110	3.02	0.43	2.14×10^{-5}	17.70 (-0.52)
	II	5.42	1.29	92		0.42	5.25×10^{-11}	10.00 (-1.30)
0.10	I	4.12	0.47	98	2.56	0.63	2.81×10^{-6}	28.10 (-0.50)
	II	5.10	1.27	88		0.61	2.34×10^{-14}	17.70 (-1.30)
0.20	I	3.78	0.46	84	2.12	0.74	1.82×10^{-6}	56.20 (-0.52)
	II	4.61	1.24	76		0.82	4.07×10^{-10}	56.20 (-1.30)
0.50	I	3.33	0.44	80	1.74	0.82	1.35×10^{-6}	100.00 (-0.52)
	II	4.27	1.22	72		0.87	3.72×10^{-10}	120.00 (-1.30)
Electrode reaction of BHC								
0.05	I	6.32	0.38	126	4.28	0.38	1.20×10^{-4}	31.60 (-0.96)
	II	14.56	1.26	160		0.36	5.25×10^{-10}	12.50 (-1.28)
0.10	I	6.14	0.33	118	4.08	0.46	1.70×10^{-4}	39.80 (-0.46)
	II	14.23	1.22	156		0.38	4.78×10^{-10}	22.30 (-1.28)
0.20	I	5.76	0.38	112	3.71	0.56	4.78×10^{-4}	50.10 (-0.46)
	II	13.66	1.18	152		0.48	2.14×10^{-11}	70.70 (-1.28)
0.50	I	5.37	0.33	108	3.40	0.64	1.41×10^{-3}	79.40 (-0.46)
	II	13.23	1.14	146		0.50	2.82×10^{-11}	120.42 (-1.28)

Fig. 1. (a) Plots of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{d,e}$. In respect of first reduction step of DDD in presence of increasing concentration of NaNO_3 : (1) 0.05, (2) 0.10, (3) 0.20 and (4) 0.50 M. (b) Plots of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{d,e}$ in respect of second reduction step of DDD in the presence of increasing concentration of NaNO_3 : (1) 0.05, (2) 0.10, (3) 0.20 and (4) 0.050 M. Each plot is shifted by -0.08 V.

increases in the case of KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , KCNS and TMAB . The same trend is observed in the values of αn_a . From this it follows that the electrode reaction of DDD is rendered more irreversible with the increasing concentrations of KCl , KBr and NH_4NO_3 , while it becomes less irreversible with the increasing concentrations of KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , KCNS and TMAB .

Electrode reaction of BHC: In this case the values of αn_a and $k_{t,h}$ increase with the increasing concentrations of KCl , KBr and TMAB while a decrease in the values occurs in the case of KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and KCNS , thereby showing that whereas the electrode reaction of BHC becomes less irreversible with the increasing concentrations of KCl , KBr and TMAB , it is rendered more irreversible in the case of KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and KCNS .

Explanation of the positive and negative shifts in $E_{1/2}$ values with increasing concentrations of different supporting electrolytes in the framework of double layer effects¹⁷: The electrode potential, i.e. the potential difference $(E - E_z)$, may be divided into two parts: (i) the potential difference (ϕ_a) between the reaction surface and bulk of the solution and (ii) the potential difference between the electrode and the reaction surface, i.e. $[(E - E_z) - \phi_a]$, where E_z is the potential of the electrocapillary zero. ϕ_a influences concentration C_a of any charged species at the reaction surface in accordance with equation (1),

$$C_a = C_b \exp[-zF\phi_a/RT] \quad (1)$$

where, z is the charge (i.e. the valency) on the reacting species and C_b is the concentration in the bulk of the solution. The potential difference between the electrode and the reaction surface, i.e. the potential $[(E - E_z) - \phi_a]$ influences the rate constant $k_{t,h}$ of the electron-transfer in accordance with equation (2),

$$k_{t,h} = k_{t,h}^* \exp[-\alpha n_a F \{(E - E_z) - \phi_a\} / RT] \quad (2)$$

in which $k_{t,h}^*$ is the heterogeneous rate constant at the potential E_z where $\phi_a = 0$. In the light of equations (1) and (2), equation (3) describes the value of the cathodic current,

$$i_c = nFAC_b k_{t,h}^* \exp[-F\{\alpha n_a(E - E_z) + (z - \alpha n_a)\} / RT] \quad (3)$$

Since in the present study the depolarisers (DDD and BHC) are uncharged species ($z=0$), the value of $(z - \alpha n_a)$ must be negative. The reduction of DDD at the d.m.e. occurs at more negative potentials than that of the electrocapillary zero, E_z which in the present study is -0.44 V (SCE). Because of this ϕ_a would be negative and would become less negative with the increasing concentrations of the supporting electrolytes¹⁸, so that the product $(z - \alpha n_a)\phi_a$ in the exponential term of equation (3) becomes less positive. To obtain the same current if C_b and A (the electrode area) are kept constant (which is actually the situation under the present study), the value of E must become more positive. Hence the wave must move towards more positive potentials on increasing the concentration of the supporting electrolytes. This explains why a positive shift occurs in $E_{1/2}$ values of DDD with the increasing concentrations of TMAB , KCNS , KNO_3 and NaNO_3 .

On the other hand, the reduction of BHC occurs at potentials more positive than E_z . Hence ϕ_a would be positive and its value decreases¹⁸ on increasing the concentration of the supporting electrolytes. This causes the product $(z - \alpha n_a)\phi_a$ in equation (3) to become less negative necessitating a shift of E towards more negative values. This explains why the $E_{1/2}$ values of BHC are rendered more negative with the increasing concentrations of KNO_3 , NaNO_3 , NH_4NO_3 and KCNS . However, in the case of TMAB , KCl and KBr , a positive shift in $E_{1/2}$ is observed which may be attributed to the specific adsorption of the anions (Br^- and Cl^-) of

these supporting electrolytes whereby these anions shift¹⁰ E_z to more negative potential. This causes the electrode potential, $(E - E_z)$ to become increasingly more positive with increasing concentrations of TMAB, KBr and KCl. From this it follows that the polarographic reduction of BHC is facilitated in the presence of increasing concentrations of TMAB, KBr and KCl resulting in a positive shift in $E_{1/2}$ values of BHC.

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